

Review article

Current limiting strategies for grid forming inverters under low voltage ride through

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ABSTRACT

Grid forming inverters are expected to play a key role in future power grids, replacing synchronous generator-based plants. However, the limited current capability of power electronics makes a difference when facing fault induced voltage sags. This work provides a comprehensive review of strategies to handle low voltage ride through events in grid forming inverters. A key contribution of this work is to differentiate between current limiting and transient stability enhancing strategies. Current limiting strategies are classified into voltage and current-based approaches according to the inverter behaviour during the fault. Their performance is evaluated attending to three criteria: (1) transient current limitation capability, related to the self-preservation of the device; and (2) fault current management and (3) transient synchronization stability, key aspects to meet grid code requirements. The modifications that are required to support the grid under asymmetrical faults are also described, focusing on the management and prioritization of positive and negative-sequence fault currents. Transient stability enhancing strategies are classified according to their implementation into (1) power synchronization loop-based and (2) current saturation-based approaches. Their main characteristics are highlighted and compared, whereas their compatibility with previous current limiting strategies is also discussed. Finally, identified open issues and challenges are covered.

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1. Introduction

In the last decades, the concern about climate change and the continuous rise in power consumption have led to an increasing integration of renewable energy resources into the electrical grid. These systems have contributed to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, increase the network power capacity and enhance the overall efficiency [1]. However, unlike traditional generation, these are mainly inverter-based resources (IBR), bringing new challenges from grid operation and management perspective [2].

Electrical grids have relied on conventional power plants, based on synchronous generators (SG), to provide grid services and ensure their reliability. SGs provide inertial response, frequency and voltage support, power oscillation damping and/or load unbalance sourcing, among other functions [3]. Furthermore, the protections and fault procedures have been designed according to the characteristics of these machines [4]. As the penetration of renewable resources increase, the ratio of IBRs will exceed that of SGs, with regions with 100% penetration of IBRs [5]. In this context, IBRs should assume the services that were previously provided by SGs.

The most common strategy for managing IBRs is the grid following (GFL) control [6]. In GFL, the inverter behaves as a controlled current source, requiring a synchronization mechanism to connect to an existing grid. The most common approach is the phase-locked loop (PLL), based on measuring the point of common coupling (PCC) voltage. GFL has shown good results in SG-dominated power grids, but its performance is limited as IBRs become dominant [7]. The inherent reduction of the grid strength and voltage stiffness will impact PLL stability [8]. Moreover, the lack of inertia produces fast frequency transients which cannot be tracked by the inner dynamics of PLLs [9].

In this context, grid forming (GFM) control has emerged as a solution to support future grids. Despite sharing the same hardware,

GFM inverters will behave as voltage sources, synchronizing with the grid through power balance. GFM inverters could replace SGs, providing synthetic inertia, stability in low strength grids and standalone operation by establishing the frequency and voltage [10]. However, even if GFM inverters are a promising solution, they are still in an early-state development, with several pilot projects evaluating their capabilities [11]. There are several challenges that need to be faced before they can be integrated into the power grid [12].

One of these challenges is the fault ride-through capability, which has been included in the top ten power system stability challenges identified by European transmission system operators in the context of MIGRATE project [13]. Among faults, literature has extensively addressed short-circuit induced voltage sags, in which GFM inverters will suffer from high overcurrents due to their voltage source behaviour. As the transient overcurrent capability of power electronics (110%–150% of rated current) is far below SGs one (>1000%) [14], current limiting strategies are required. These strategies should not only protect inverter hardware from overcurrents, but they are also required to meet grid code requirements, by keeping the inverter synchronized with the grid (transient synchronization stability) and supporting voltage recovery through fault currents [15].

The aim of this work is to fill the gap related to low voltage ride-through (LVRT) strategies in GFM inverters, providing an overview of the strategies that can limit the current and enhance the transient stability during these events. Current limiting strategies have already been discussed in previous reviews [12,16,17]. However, these works were not focused on LVRT, lacking a detailed comparative and evaluation. These strategies have also been evaluated attending to different criteria, such as transient current limitation capability [18,19], fault current control [20] and transient stability [19,21]. However, none of them have gathered all of these topics together and the number of evaluated strategies was limited. Additionally to current limiting approaches, strategies to improve transient synchronization stability

Nomenclature**Abbreviations**

APS	Adaptive power synchronization
CS	Current saturation
GFL	Grid following
GFM	Grid forming
IBR	Inverter-based resource
LVRT	Low voltage ride through
MS	Mode switching
PCC	Point of common coupling
PLL	Phase-locked loop
PRM	Power reference modification
PSL	Power synchronization loop
RPC	Reactive power control
SEP	Stable equilibrium point
SG	Synchronous generator
TVA	Threshold virtual admittance
TVI	Threshold virtual impedance
UEP	Unstable equilibrium point
VPA	Virtual power angle
VS	Voltage saturation

Symbols

ΔV	Voltage magnitude difference between internal voltage reference and PCC voltage
δ	Virtual power angle
γ	Phase difference between the PLL output and PCC voltage
ω	Angular frequency
σ	Reactance to resistance ratio
τ	Time constant of the grid impedance
θ	Internal angle
φ	current phase, referred to d axis
D	Damping coefficient
E	Internal voltage reference
H	Inertia constant
I	Current magnitude
i	Current vector
L	Inductance
P	Active power
Q	Reactive power
R	Resistance
v	Voltage vector
X	Reactance
Z	Impedance

Superscripts

*	Setpoint
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Subscripts

c	Converter-side signal
eq	Equivalent. Value measured between inverter to grid
f	Filter value
g	Grid signal
lim	Limited signal

max	Maximum value
o	Capacitor-side signal
pcc	Point of common coupling signal
th	Threshold value
u	Unstable
v	Virtual

during faults have been also addressed in literature. In some cases, current limiting and stability enhancing strategies were mixed without a clear differentiation [22,23]. Transient enhancing approaches were discussed in [24], but their compatibility with current limiting strategies was not addressed. Finally, [25] described some current limiting and stability enhancing strategies, but no classification was provided. Compared to previous works (Table 1), the main contributions of this study are:

- Providing a classification of LVRT strategies attending to their target: (1) current limitation and (2) transient stability enhancement.
- Classifying the existing current limiting strategies into voltage-based and current-based approaches. The strategies inside each group are also categorized into subgroups. The performance from self-preservation and grid code requirements perspective is evaluated.
- Describing the modified current limiting strategies that can provide positive and negative-sequence fault current contribution for asymmetrical faults.
- Classifying the existing transient stability enhancing strategies. These are classified into two groups depending on their implementation, and compatibility with current limiting strategies is addressed.

The research methodology was comprised of three key steps. First, the topic was discussed and existing grid code requirements were identified. Then, literature was searched and screened. The literature which was most related to GFM inverters and LVRT strategies was left, based on title, abstract and full text. Finally, the identified articles were analysed and summarized according to the structure of the review, which is presented in Fig. 1. Section 2 overviews LVRT requirements for IBRs. Section 3 describes and classifies GFM current limiting strategies. Following this, Section 4 compares their performance attending to transient current, fault current management and stability perspective. Section 5 explores the modifications that provide independent positive and negative-sequence fault current control under asymmetrical faults. Section 6 classifies and compares the strategies that can enhance the synchronization stability during the LVRT event. Section 7 covers some open issues, whereas the conclusions are summed up in Section 8.

2. LVRT requirements

First grid codes were focused on protecting IBRs, disconnecting them under disturbances. However, as the share of IBRs increase, this approach could lead to instability and cascaded failures [27]. Current grid codes are requiring IBRs to support the grid during LVRT events. The expected behaviour of a GFM inverter during a fault, given in Fig. 2, could be summarized in three targets: (1) self-preserving the inverter, (2) keeping synchronized to the grid and (3) contributing with a fault current.

2.1. Self-preservation

IBRs must limit the current magnitude during a fault to protect the semiconductors and prevent an overcurrent tripped disconnection.

Fig. 1. Structure of the review.

Table 1
Topics covered in other reviews.

References	LVRT requirements	Current limiting strategies	Performance of current limiting strategies			Asymmetrical faults	Stability improving strategies
			Current transient	Fault contribution	Transient stability		
[13,26]	x						
[17,22]		x					
[23,24]		x					x
[18]		x	x				
[20]		x	x	x			
[16]		x				x	
[19]		x	x		x		
[25]		x					x
[12]		x			x	x	
This review	x	x	x	x	x	x	x

Fig. 2. Converter current and grid voltage evolution of a GFM inverter during a voltage sag.

Transient current limitation is critical during the first cycles after the sag. Unlike GFL inverters, GFM inverters behaving as voltage sources

will be prone to overcurrents due to the voltage difference between the inverter terminal and the PCC voltage.

2.2. Grid synchronization

The disconnection of IBRs during LVRT events is determined based on a voltage-time pattern, depending on both PCC voltage sag and its duration. Most countries have their own grid code requirements, including the operating voltage range, fault duration and restoration time [28,29]. International organizations like IEEE have also published relevant requirements for IBRs. For instance, IEEE 1547-2018 brought certain regulations for the interconnection and interoperability between distribution grids and distributed energy resources [30]. Regulations for interconnecting IBRs and transmission grids are covered in IEEE 2800-2022 [31]. Some voltage-time curves are shown in Fig. 3. IBRs should stay connected and synchronized with the grid if the PCC voltage transient is above the line.

From synchronization perspective, the challenge in GFL inverters is linked to the instability caused by PLL dynamics, whereas GFM inverters might desynchronize due to power balance loss. It is critical for the stability of the grid that IBRs keep synchronized during the

Fig. 3. Voltage vs. time LVRT requirements for different standards.

event. Once the fault is cleared, they should restore normal operation in a seamless approach, without power oscillations that could perturb other devices.

2.3. Fault current contribution

IBRs should contribute to restore the voltage during a fault. Some specific national grid codes (Spanish [32], German [33]), and international standards (IEEE 2800-2022) are requiring IBRs to support the grid both during symmetrical and asymmetrical faults. This is achieved by injecting a positive-sequence capacitive current to increase voltage magnitude, and a negative-sequence inductive current to reduce voltage unbalance in asymmetrical faults. In all cases, fault currents should be proportional to the magnitude of the positive and negative-sequence PCC voltage. The exact proportion depends on specific system operator requirements.

Grid codes are also requiring maximum utilization of IBRs current capacity. Active power exchange can also be required to meet this condition. According to [31], IBRs should have both active and reactive current prioritization strategies, being the latter the default. Other requirements such as the current step time response and settling time are usually defined in each grid code.

GFL inverters can achieve fault current control by modifying the current setpoint according to measured PCC voltage. However, such strategy is not straightforward in GFM inverters due to its voltage source behaviour, and new strategies are required.

2.4. Summary

The trend in all the IBR-related grid codes is similar. They are invariant with respect to the type of energy source, inverter topology and control strategy [34]. Hence, GFM and GFL inverters should meet the same LVRT requirements. A long as compliance with standards is concerned, the performance at the inverter terminal is the only criterion that must be satisfied. This has led to the development of several LVRT strategies for GFM inverters.

In this context, latest UNIFI [35] and AEMO [36] reports have pointed that some requirements are not practical for GFM inverters under some circumstances, and exceptions should be warranted (under the agreement of manufacturers, developers and system operators) until standards can be updated to fully account for them.

3. Classification of current limiting strategies

The simplified diagram of a grid-connected GFM inverter is shown in Fig. 4. The inverter is connected to the grid using a typical LC filter and a coupling transformer. The grid is represented as its Thévenin equivalent circuit, with a grid impedance Z_g and a voltage source v_g . For the sake of simplicity, the inverter is fed with an ideal DC voltage source, representing a single-stage or a double-stage IBR with negligible DC bus dynamics. The GFM controller includes two control layers:

Fig. 4. Simplified diagram of a grid-connected GFM inverter.

1. Outer loop: composed of a Power Synchronization Loop (PSL) and a Reactive Power Control (RPC). The former generates the angular frequency ω using active power balance, whereas the latter will generate the internal voltage reference amplitude E based on reactive power balance. Outer loop strategies can be classified into droop controllers, synchronous machine based controllers, and non-linear synchronization methods [37].
2. Inner loop: It will use outer loops outputs to generate the modulation voltage v_c^* . Inner controllers include direct voltage synthesis, single voltage controller or cascaded voltage-current controller [38,39]. The latter is shown in Fig. 4.

GFM current limiting strategies can be classified to two main groups: hardware-based and software-based. Hardware-based limiters are an effective and fast way to limit current, but they add extra hardware components and strong distortion due to pulse inhibition [40,41]. Software-based limiters provide high flexibility from current limitation perspective. However, they will be limited by the bandwidth and delay of the controller. This section will focus on software-based strategies, which can be classified into: (1) current-based and (2) voltage-based limiters [16].

3.1. Current-based limiters

Current-based limiters, or direct limiters, will prioritize current control over voltage one. When active, the inverter will lose voltage source behaviour, turning into a controlled current source. Current-based limiters provide a precise control over the output current, at the cost of reduced transient stability. Moreover, they rely on the existence of an inner current controller. Two main strategies can be found:

3.1.1. Mode switching

The mode switching (MS) strategy switches the operation from GFM to GFL during the fault, as shown in Fig. 5. Once the fault clearance is detected by the controller, the inverter switches back to GFM. While in GFL, the inverter is synchronized to the grid through an auxiliary PLL. Its main advantage is that active and reactive currents can be properly managed during the fault. However, apart from losing the voltage source behaviour, its performance will rely on the PLL, making it less reliable under deep sags or weak grids.

MS requires an accurate trip signal to transition between modes, increasing implementation complexity. Fault detection algorithms can be based on current [42] or PCC voltage [43]. The seamless transition from GFL to GFM once the fault is cleared is critical to ensure a proper fault recovery [44,45].

3.1.2. Current saturation

In the current saturation (CS), the current limiter is embedded inside the inner control, as shown in Fig. 6. The current setpoint at the output of the voltage controller is saturated to the maximum allowable current, I_{max} . Unlike MS, the angular frequency is derived from the PSL, without an auxiliary PLL. Moreover, there is no need for a tripping signal nor mode switching.

Fig. 5. Mode switching (MS) simplified diagram.

Fig. 6. Current saturation (CS) simplified diagram.

The main drawback of CS is the need of a cascaded control structure. Cascaded controllers require sufficient separation between bandwidths, which might not be feasible in high-power and low-switching frequencies. Moreover, they have been identified as a source of instability [46]. Modified CS strategies that remove the cascaded structure have been proposed. In [47,48], the current controller is seamlessly bypassed under regular conditions. In [49], a parallel voltage and current controller structure with automatic transition is suggested.

Current saturation strategies Depending on the saturation approach, three CS algorithms are identified [20]. They are represented in Fig. 7:

1. Instantaneous saturation
2. Magnitude-based saturation
3. Priority-based saturation

Instantaneous saturation uses an element-wise saturation. It is usually implemented in natural reference frame abc , specially in 4-wire systems, where phase currents can be controlled independently [12]. To prevent the harmonic distortion produced by sinusoidal setpoints clipping, root-mean square values can be used, but transient current limitation is worsened [13]. Instantaneous saturation in $\alpha\beta$ stationary frame or dq rotary frame require conservative limits that reduce the maximum current usage. Hence, magnitude and the priority-based saturation are preferred.

Magnitude-based saturation, or circular limiter, limits the magnitude of the original setpoint while keeping the phase unaltered [50]. It can be implemented both in $\alpha\beta$ [51] and dq [52] frames. Priority-based saturation does not only limit the magnitude, but it can also force the phase to the desired angle φ . Due to its simplicity, dq frame is used [53]. Magnitude and priority-based saturation prevent clipping and maximize the current capability during fault. Priority saturation is prone to higher oscillations, but it adds an extra degree of freedom to improve transient stability [54].

3.2. Voltage-based limiters

In voltage-based limiters, or indirect limiters, the inverter keeps the voltage source behaviour. The current is controlled indirectly by actuating over the voltage setpoint. Compared to current-based limiters, they provide higher flexibility from inner controller perspective, removing the need of current regulators [55]. They also provide better transient stability, at the cost of a higher transient overcurrent.

3.2.1. Threshold virtual impedance

The virtual impedance provides the ability to emulate a non-physical impedance, and it has already been used for filter resonance damping, power flow control, load sharing, ... [56]. In the threshold virtual impedance (TVI), the equivalent impedance between the inverter and the PCC is virtually increased to limit the current. The equivalent simplified circuit is shown in Fig. 8. All the impedances but Z_v are physical.

TVIs are mainly implemented in $\alpha\beta$ or dq frames, but they have also been proposed in abc frame [57]. To prevent sudden impedance changes, TVIs are usually implemented using a linear approach, starting at a threshold current magnitude I_{th} . The linear relation between the current and the virtual impedance (resistance, R_v and reactance, X_v) [58]:

$$R_v = \begin{cases} 0 & |i_c| \leq I_{th} \\ K_v(|i_c| - I_{th}) & |i_c| > I_{th} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$X_v = L_v \omega = \sigma R_v \quad (2)$$

Reactance to resistance ratio, σ , is a design degree of freedom. A value between 5 and 10 provides proper decoupling of active/reactive power, and damping of synchronous oscillations [59]. The linear gain K_v is selected to limit current magnitude to I_{max} under a maximum preset voltage magnitude difference, ΔV_{max} , between E and v_o (3).

$$K_v \sqrt{\sigma^2 + 1} (I_{max} - I_{th}) \geq \frac{\Delta V_{max}}{I_{max}} \quad (3)$$

The preset ΔV_{max} introduces a trade-off between current limitation capability and stability. Small values do not ensure current limitation under severe voltage sags, whereas large values can produce instability issues due to the high impedance. Additionally, TVI performance will depend on grid impedance, as the sag depth depends on it. Non-linear TVIs can also be implemented by adding exponential terms to (1). Non-linear TVIs operate closer to the maximum current, improving fault-current provision [60].

Threshold virtual impedance strategies TVIs can be implemented using impedance or admittance approach. Moreover, impedance can be placed at two different locations. Simplified diagrams are given in Fig. 9.

1. Impedance-based

- (a) External: Voltage drop is applied to the setpoints of the outer control, before inner controller.
- (b) Internal: Voltage drop is applied to the modulation voltage, after inner controller.

2. Admittance-based, or threshold virtual admittance (TVA)

Impedance-based approaches apply a voltage drop according to the measured converter current i_c . The external TVI works with the hypothesis that the voltage setpoint is tracked fast by the controller. However, its bandwidth can be below 50 Hz in high power applications [61]. The internal TVI provides a faster response, but it requires an anti-windup of the inner regulators. An alternative approach is to apply both internal and external TVI to prevent windup issues [62,63]. If there is no inner controller, external and internal impedances are equivalent [64]. Impedance-based strategies are usually implemented using quasi-stationary terms, removing the derivative terms that produce noise amplification. Quasi-stationary impedance could turn synchronous oscillations into sub-synchronous, endangering stability [65].

The admittance-based approach emulates the static and dynamic behaviour of an impedance without derivative terms [66]. It is based on the output voltage v_o measurement and a low-pass filter [67]. The impedance is ensured within the bandwidth of the current controller, achieving a dynamic performance between the external and internal TVI. As drawbacks, it requires a current controller and a minimum impedance to operate [57].

Fig. 7. Current saturation types.

Fig. 8. Equivalent circuit of a GFM inverter with a threshold virtual impedance.

3.2.2. Voltage saturation

Voltage saturation (VS) limits the current indirectly through the limitation of the voltage E and the angle θ of the outer controllers. This is achieved by meeting Eq. (4), where the magnitude of the difference between E and v_{pcc} must be lower than the voltage drop produced by I_{max} . The voltage drop includes physical and virtual impedances. A simplified diagram is shown in Fig. 10.

$$|E - v_{pcc}| = |(Z_t + Z_v)I_{max}| \quad (4)$$

One of the main drawbacks of VS is that it performs the current limitation in open loop, without current measurements. Hence, it is subjected to errors due to impedance uncertainties and tolerances. This problem is minimized if the virtual impedance is predominant, but power exchange capability will be limited [20].

Voltage saturation strategies Depending on the signals which are saturated, two VS strategies are found. Their simplified diagrams are given in Fig. 11.

1. Phase & amplitude VS (PA-VS)
2. Amplitude VS (A-VS)

The PA-VS (Fig. 11(a)) limits both the magnitude and angle of the internal voltage, using v_{pcc} amplitude and phase information, for which a PLL is required [68,69]. Magnitude is limited to a maximum voltage drop magnitude ΔV_{max} , whereas the phase shift between E and v_{pcc} is limited to δ_{max} . These limits can be fixed according to the maximum active and reactive power at rated operation. However, adaptive limits have proved to be more effective to improve the current transient response, satisfy the grid code currents, or maximize fault current [70,71].

The performance of PA-VS might degrade under weak grids due to the PLL dynamics. A-VS can remove this element by only limiting the magnitude of the internal voltage (Fig. 11(b)) [72]. As a drawback, the current limitation is only valid against voltage sags, losing protection against other events, e.g., phase jumps. The angle can be indirectly limited using a power limiter based on v_{pcc} magnitude [73].

3.3. Summary

The characteristics of current limiting strategies are summed in Table 2. These have been classified into current-based (MS and CS) and voltage-based limiters (TVI and VS).

From implementation perspective, MS is identified as the most complex strategy. It requires a fault detection algorithm, an auxiliary PLL to operate during fault, a proper strategy to seamlessly switch from GFL to GFM and an anti-windup due to the saturation of the inner voltage controller. The remaining strategies will not switch from operation mode, and hence, they remove the fault detection and mode switching algorithm. CS strategies will also remove the need of an auxiliary PLL to operate, but they still require an inner current controller and anti-windup for the cascaded controller.

Voltage-based limiters provide higher flexibility and less complexity, specially in the case of the external TVI and the A-VS. These strategies do not depend on a current limiter nor auxiliary PLL, acting only on the internal voltage reference with minor modifications. Exceptions are the TVA and the PA-VS. In the case of the TVA, a current controller is still required, but inner voltage controller saturation is prevented. The PA-VS removes the need of a current controller, but it relies on an auxiliary PLL to limit the phase shift during the fault.

Regardless of the current-based or voltage-based approach, the strategies which rely on a PLL will be more susceptible to grid conditions, such as impedance or voltage sag depth, than those which depend on PSL. TVIs, which use the PSL during fault, will be also more sensitivity to grid conditions because they are tuned for a preset voltage sag depth.

Table 3 gathers the current limiting strategies proposed in literature. CS strategies are the most common approach for LVRT, and both magnitude and priority-based approach are extensively used. In the case of voltage-based limiters, external TVI is the main strategy. Finally, some authors propose hybrid strategies, in which current-based (CS) and voltage-based (TVI) approaches are used together.

4. Performance of current limiting strategies

As it has been discussed in Section 2, GFM inverters should achieve three targets during a LVRT event: (1) preventing transient overcurrents that could produce internal damage or tripping the device, (2) keeping synchronized with grid during and after the fault and (3) providing a fault current to support voltage recovery. However, the performance of the GFM inverter will vary depending on the current limiting strategy.

4.1. Transient overcurrent limitation

The transient overcurrent limitation capability will mainly depend on the current or voltage source behaviour of the inverter during the fault.

Fig. 9. Threshold virtual impedance strategies.

Table 2
Main characteristics of current limiting strategies.

	MS	CS	TVI			VS	
			External	Internal	Admittance	PA	A
Behaviour	Current	Current	Voltage	Voltage	Voltage	Voltage	Voltage
Fault & mode switch	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
Synchronization method	PLL	PSL	PSL	PSL	PSL	PLL	PSL
Cascaded controller	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
Inner controller saturation	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	No
Sensitivity to grid conditions	High	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium	High	Low
Complexity	High	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low

Table 3
Current limiting strategies in literature.

Current limiting strategy	References	
Mode switching (MS)	[19,46,74–76]	
Current saturation (CS)	Instantaneous	[42,49,77–79]
	Magnitude-based	[18,20,47,50,51,54,80–86]
	Priority-based	[19,20,53,54,86–95]
Threshold virtual impedance (TVI)	External	[18–20,58,60,64,86,93,96–99]
	Internal	[62,63,100]
	Admittance	[57]
Voltage saturation (VS)	Phase & amplitude	[20,68–71]
	Phase	[72,73,101,102]
Hybrid strategy (CS + TVI)	[103–107]	

Fig. 10. Voltage saturation (VS) simplified diagram.

4.1.1. Current-based limiters

MS and CS will turn the inverter into a controlled current source, providing a similar performance to GFL inverters.

In CS, as the current limitation is embedded in the inner controller, the transient overcurrent will depend on the bandwidth and damping of the current regulator. In this context, hysteresis-based regulators can minimize the transient, at the cost of a variable switching frequency [77]. In MS, the transient overcurrent will also depend on the delay introduced by fault detection and mode switching algorithms. During this delay, the voltage source behaviour is kept, increasing the current transient [70].

4.1.2. Voltage-based limiters

Due to the voltage source behaviour of these limiters, the transient current control is not straightforward. Fig. 12 shows the simplified equivalent circuit of a grid-connected GFM inverter, modelled using two voltage sources and an equivalent impedance Z_{eq} . Initially, the system is operating in the steady state conditions determined by the phasors (upper arrow) in the figure. At t_0 , a fault will lead to new operating conditions, identified using an apostrophe ('). The current

waveforms before and during the fault are also shown. The current will be the sum of a transient and steady state term [108]:

- The steady state term, i'_{cs} , only depends on post-fault voltages and impedance (5). φ' is the phase shift of the current after the fault.

$$i'_{cs}(t) = \sqrt{2} \left| \frac{\bar{E}' - \bar{V}'_g}{Z'_{eq}} \right| \sin(\omega t + \varphi') \quad (5)$$

- The transient term, i'_{ct} , depends on the instantaneous voltage values at fault time (6). It decays exponentially according to the time constant $\tau' = L'_{eq}/R'_{eq}$, which depends on the inductance to resistance ratio during fault conditions.

$$i'_{ct}(t) = \left(\sqrt{2} \left| \frac{\bar{E} - \bar{V}'_g}{Z_{eq}} \right| \sin(\omega t_0 + \varphi) + \sqrt{2} \left| \frac{\bar{E}' - \bar{V}'_g}{Z'_{eq}} \right| \sin(\omega t_0 + \varphi') \right) e^{-t/\tau'} \quad (6)$$

Voltage-based limiters can limit the steady state term of the current, but the transient term is uncontrolled and it will naturally decay according to τ' [101]. TVIs can reduce this time constant and damp overcurrents faster by increasing the virtual resistance. However, this approach will deteriorate the transient stability, coupling active and reactive powers [109]. To limit the impact on transient stability, a dynamic virtual resistance based on a high-pass filter is proposed in [58]. VSs cannot modify the impedance, and hence, will suffer from long transients, specially in highly inductive lines.

Additionally, voltage-based limiters will usually react slower than current-based ones. In voltage-based limiters, the control action takes

Fig. 11. Voltage saturation types.

Fig. 12. Current transient of a grid-connected GFM inverter using a voltage-based limiter.

places at the input of the voltage controller rather than in the inner current controller. The bandwidth of voltage controller will be lower, specially in cascaded inner structures. TVA or internal TVI can provide an increased bandwidth by bypassing the voltage controller, at the cost of an increased complexity (addition of inner current controller, and anti-windup strategy in internal TVI). The transient current control will be further deteriorated in PA-VS, as its performance will also depend on the time that the PLL needs to track and settle v_{pcc} .

4.2. Fault current control

To meet the fault current requirements of the latest grid codes, current limiting strategies should be capable of operating at maximum current capacity, and provide independent control over active and reactive currents. They should also manage positive and negative-sequence currents. The latter requirement will be covered in Section 5.

4.2.1. Current-based limiters

As GFL control, these limiters can dynamically modify the current setpoints attending to measured v_{pcc} . These strategies can maximize the current usage of the inverter, but the current controllability will be determined by the synchronization mechanism.

In MS, the auxiliary PLL will keep the inverter synchronized with the grid. While synchronized, active and reactive currents can be managed independently. However, the PLL dynamics might deteriorate as the voltage sag depth or grid impedance increases, introducing some coupling between currents.

In CS, the PSL is kept as synchronization mechanism. Priority-based limiters have been proposed to handle the current limits according to the grid codes [54]. However, when the current limiter is triggered, the active power balance of the PSL will be lost and the internal voltage will not be aligned with the controller reference anymore. In these conditions, the angle difference between the current and the voltage cannot be specified precisely, coupling active and reactive currents. An additional strategy that ensures the PSL power balance is required to gain control over active and reactive currents. Instantaneous and magnitude-based limiters cannot be used directly to meet fault current requirements, as they will only modify the magnitude of current setpoint which is determined by the voltage controller.

4.2.2. Voltage-based limiters

Preserving the voltage source behaviour provides a natural current response to voltage perturbations [80]. This is translated into a fast current injection capability during sags, with response times below 5 ms according to [110].

In TVIs, active and reactive current contribution will be determined by the internal voltage and the grid voltage magnitude and phase, and the overall impedance. As the TVIs are designed to handle the worst disturbance, small voltage sags (e.g., distant fault) will not use the full capacity of the converter. This problem might be alleviated by using non-linear TVIs, which operate closer to the rated current. Moreover, the TVI should be dynamically modified to meet fault current requirements, which could impact the stability of the grid and requires additional grid impedance estimation algorithms.

In VSs, having phase and amplitude information through a PLL (PA-VS) can provide a proper control active and reactive currents during faults. In A-VS, a dynamic active power limiter needs to be added to prevent power balance loss and ensure proper current injection. In general, using dynamic limitations in A-VS has shown good results in meeting fault current contribution in a simple and effective way [73]. However, the dynamics of the active power limiter might considerably reduce in high inertial systems, making it not suitable for LVRT events. As VSs limit the current in open loop, they require some current margin for component tolerances and uncertainties, reducing maximum current usage.

4.3. Transient synchronization stability

Current limiting strategies will also impact transient synchronization stability of GFM inverters, that is, their capability to keep synchronized with the grid during the LVRT event. Their transient stability has been evaluated through different non-linear approaches such as Lyapunov direct method [111], phase portrait [112] or virtual power angle (VPA) [21]. This work will focus on VPA method, a quasi-static approach based on the phase difference between E and v_g , known as virtual power angle, δ . This method can evaluate the transient stability in a graphic and intuitive approach, in a similar way to SGs.

The VPA curves of a GFM inverter without current limitation are given in Fig. 13. For simplicity, a symmetrical fault is considered, with the same pre-fault and post-fault curves. In a purely inductive grid, active power is determined by (7), being X_{eq} the overall reactance between the inverter and the grid. A GFM inverter with a swing-based PSL is considered, in which the dynamics of ω are determined by (8) in per unit [113]. P^* and P are the power setpoint and feedback, H the inertia constant, D_p the damping coefficient and ω_g the grid angular frequency, which can be considered constant.

$$P = \frac{E|v_g|}{X_{eq}} \sin \delta \quad (7)$$

Fig. 13. VPA curves during normal operation and fault condition.

Fig. 14. VPA curves during a fault using MS.

$$2H \frac{d\omega}{dt} = \frac{P^*}{\omega} - \frac{P}{\omega} - D_p(\omega_g - \omega) \quad (8)$$

During normal operation, the intersection between the pre-fault power curve and the power setpoint provides a stable equilibrium point (SEP), a . Under a fault, the power curve is reduced proportionally to v_g magnitude. A deep sag will lead to no SEP, moving the operation point from a to b . The power unbalance of the PSL will increase δ , depending its rate of change mainly on the power unbalance and the inertia. Damping power has a negligible effect. Once the fault is cleared at c , v_g is restored and the operation point jumps to d . At this point, P is higher than P^* , but δ will still increase due to the inertial behaviour. The maximum angle δ_{max} is reached at e . The GFM inverter will keep synchronized if $\delta_{max} < \delta_u$, known as the Unstable Equilibrium Point (UEP). In that case, δ will decrease and return back to point a . The stability of inertial systems is calculated using equal area criterion, for which the deceleration area (A_d) must be equal or higher than the acceleration area (A_a).

4.3.1. Mode switching

MS has to face two challenges from transient stability perspective: (1) ensuring the synchronization stability of the GFL during the fault and (2) providing a fast and seamless transition to GFM when fault is cleared.

The stability of GFL inverters is limited under deep voltage sags and weak grid conditions [114]. One method to evaluate their stability is through $|v_g| - \gamma$ curves, where γ is the phase shift between the PLL output and the grid voltage [19,115]. The transient stability equations are equivalent to VPA ones (8), including a virtual inertia H_v , a virtual voltage reference v_v^* and a virtual damping D_v . The curves are shown in Fig. 14.

$$2H_v \frac{d^2\gamma}{dt} = v_v^* - |v_g| \sin \gamma - D_v \frac{d\gamma}{dt} \quad (9)$$

The stability in MS can be boosted by increasing H_v and D_v . This is achieved by increasing the proportional gain or reducing the integral gain of the PLL [24]. A SEP can also be ensured by modifying v_v^* , which depends on the reactive current and the grid impedance [116].

Once the fault is cleared, the transition from GFL to GFM is critical. During the fault, the angle of the PSL will move away from the angle locked by the PLL. A direct transition to GFM could lead to overcurrents and power oscillations, re-triggering the fault condition. To solve this issue, several re-synchronization strategies have been proposed in literature: voltage zero-crossing, dynamic PSL [75], virtual impedance [42] and angle tracking synchronization loop [117]. Regardless of the strategy, the re-synchronization requires some time due to the internal dynamics of the PSL, enlarging the recovery time and endangering frequency stability [78].

Table 4

Active power under different CS strategies, in per unit.

CS strategy	Active power (P_{CS})
Magnitude-based [102]	$\frac{E v_g I_{max} \sin(\delta)}{\sqrt{E^2 + v_g ^2 - 2E v_g \cos(\delta)}}$
Priority-based [87]	$ v_g I_{max} \cos(\delta - \varphi)$

4.3.2. Current saturation

During the fault, the power converter operates in current control mode while the PSL realizes the synchronization with the grid. Due to the current saturation, the voltage and the outer controllers are out of the loop. The active power curve will depend on the CS strategy, summed in Table 4.

The VPA curves of a GFM inverter with CS under a fault are given in Fig. 15. Under a voltage sag, the reactive current flowing through the power converter will increase, activating the current saturation. The control will enter the CS mode, reaching point b . The fault recovery will depend on the δ at which fault is cleared, d . Two scenarios exist depending if the fault is cleared before or after δ crosses “Post-fault w/ CS” and “Pre-fault” curve intersection. If the fault is cleared before, the controller exits CS and the fault recovery dynamics will be determined by PSL. If the fault is cleared after, CS will be active after fault clearing and the recovery time will be increased due to CS associated dynamics.

The inverter will keep synchronized if δ_{max} does not cross δ_{uc} (UEP). Once the angular frequency decreases, CS is disabled (f) returning to stable operation point a . If the inner voltage controller does not include an anti-windup strategy, CS may not exit, endangering the stability of the system [118]. The stability criteria for inertia-less GFM inverters using CS has been analytically obtained in [91].

The power curve shape of CS will reduce the stability of the power converter ($\delta_{uc} < \delta_u$) [89]. In priority-based CS, φ is a degree of freedom that can be used to enhance the transient stability. Increasing its value will shift the “Fault w/ CS” curve to the right, decreasing the acceleration area and increasing the deceleration area. The transient stability against phase jumps will also be boosted. The optimal φ from transient stability perspective is constrained by the ability of the controller to switch back to voltage mode after the fault. According to [90], 45° provides a good trade-off in most operating conditions (Fig. 15(b)). If φ is set to improve transient stability, grid code fault current requirements might not be met.

Opposite to prior knowledge, some authors have shown that magnitude-based CS could retain voltage source behaviour. When it used with a virtual admittance, the limiter will act as an impedance amplifying module, behaving as a voltage source behind a variable impedance [81]. Similarly, when voltage controller dynamics are considered, a variable virtual resistor behaviour is achieved [82]. In this case, the power converter capability is maximized when the angle of the virtual impedance matches grid impedance [83].

Fig. 15. VPA curves during a fault using CS.

Fig. 16. VPA curves with constant Z_{eq} and decreasing reactance to resistance ratios (σ).

Fig. 17. VPA curves during a fault using TVI.

4.3.3. Threshold virtual impedance

The TVI will virtually modify the equivalent impedance while keeping the voltage source behaviour of the inverter. The synchronization is carried out through the PSL, but its windup can endanger the stability.

The active power equation of a GFM inverter with a TVI is given by (10). The equation considers both resistive and inductive terms, as the TVI could modify the overall resistance R_{eq} and inductance X_{eq} seen by the system [103]. In a purely inductive grid, $R_{eq} = R_v$. Increasing R_v will reduce σ , which has a two-fold effect: It will attenuate active power curve, reducing transient stability (Fig. 16). However, as previously discussed, it will contribute to damp current transients faster, limiting the overcurrent and reducing post-fault oscillations.

$$P_{TVI} = \frac{E|v_g|}{Z_{eq}} \sin\left(\arctan\left(\frac{R_{eq}}{X_{eq}}\right) + \delta\right) - \frac{|v_g|^2 R_{eq}}{Z_{eq}^2} \quad (10)$$

The VPA curves are plotted in Fig. 17. For simplicity, an inductive TVI is considered. When the voltage sag occurs and the TVI is activated (b), the $P-\delta$ curve maintains a sine form, but with a reduced amplitude due to the reduction of v_g amplitude and the increase of Z_{eq} [87]. As in CS, two fault recovery scenarios are identified. When the fault is cleared before reaching rated power P_m , the virtual impedance is disabled and the inverter recovers according to PSL dynamics. If δ is cleared after, the TVI will be active once the fault is cleared, producing a larger transient. After the inertial overshoot, the TVI will be progressively removed as the current reduces from I_{max} (f) to I_{th} (d). Finally, the TVI is disabled and the pre-fault value, a, is reached.

Compared with a GFM inverter without current limitation, the TVI will reduce the UEP angle, $\delta_{uv} < \delta_u$. However, TVI will keep the sine form of the active power due to the voltage source behaviour, outperforming CS not only against voltage sags, but also phase jumps.

The stability criteria for inertia-less GFM inverters has been analytically obtained in [96].

Asymmetrical virtual impedances have been proposed to provide higher flexibility and reshape the active power curve in TVI-based GFM inverters. By using different inductance in dq axes, a reluctance power similar to the one produced in salient SGs can be achieved [119]. A proper asymmetrical impedance design can improve the stability margins of GFM inverters [120].

4.3.4. Voltage saturation

The transient stability of PA-VS has been limited to simulation due to the complexity of the analytical approach [69]. All in all, this strategy requires a proper anti-windup of the outer loops to ensure the recovery from the faults. Moreover, as it depends on a PLL, it is expected to have limited performance under weak grids.

The A-VS will only limit E amplitude to prevent an excessive reactive current during voltage sags [72]. As the internal voltage is limited to a value which is lower than the pre-fault value, $E_{lim} < E$, its $P-\delta$ curve will keep a sine form with limited amplitude:

$$P_{VS} = \frac{E_{lim}|v_g|}{X_{eq}} \sin \delta \quad (11)$$

The VPA curves of a GFM inverter with an A-VS under a fault are given in Fig. 18. The analysis is similar to the one carried out for Fig. 13. Even if the UEP angle δ_u is kept constant, the transient stability is worsened. The reason is that the active power curve during the fault is reduced, increasing the acceleration area. Moreover, if the fault is cleared with a δ above the rated power, an overloading condition will occur. To prevent overloading and ensure synchronization, A-VS usually includes a dynamic active power setpoint limiter which depends on v_{pcc} [73]. Under an ideal behaviour, without delays and a perfect

Fig. 18. VPA curves during a fault using A-VS.

power setpoint calculation, this approach could provide a SEP close to point *b* during the fault.

The A-VS will not protect against phase jumps. Under these events, the response of the inverter will depend on the PSL dynamics. High inertia constants could lead to instability in these conditions [84].

4.4. Summary

The performance of current limiting strategies are summed in Table 5. MS and PA-VS are feasible solutions to meet LVRT grid code requirements in SG-dominated grids. Under strong grids, they will provide full control of fault currents and boosted transient stability due to the PLL dynamics and performance. As drawbacks, PA-VS will suffer from high transient overcurrents and it will not maximize inverter current capacity. In the case of MS, its implementation complexity is higher, requiring fault detection and mode switching algorithms. Moreover, as IBRs become dominant, and grid strength weakens, MS and PA-VS performance will deteriorate, making them not suitable to meet previous requirements. Finally, these strategies are not valid under islanded scenarios, requiring an existing grid to operate.

CS, TVI and A-VS will rely on the PSL rather than PLL to synchronize, making them less susceptible to grid conditions. CS strategies offer the best transient overcurrent limitation and maximize current usage. However, their reduced transient stability makes it challenging to meet grid code-required synchronization times. Priority-based CS can modify the current setpoint phase to boost the stability. It can also be used to manage fault current contribution, but active and reactive currents will be decoupled due to PSL power unbalance. Additional strategies that ensure PSL power balance during fault are required (Section 6).

TVIs can ensure longer synchronization time, but they cannot maximize current usage during shallow sags, making it difficult to meet fault current contribution requirement. A A-VS could achieve similar performance to PA-VS depending on PSL dynamics, but its protection is limited to voltage sags.

A single current limiting strategy might not be sufficient to meet all the LVRT requirements. Hybridizing current limiting strategies by using both voltage-based limiters and CS together is another approach [103, 105, 106]. CS will provide transient overcurrent limitation, whereas the slower voltage-based limiter will ensure the voltage source behaviour and improve transient stability. Despite the advantages of hybrid strategies, the complexity of the controller is increased. Moreover, it does not solve the fault current controllability issue, requiring additional control actions. All in all, meeting all LVRT targets in a simple and straightforward way is still an open issue.

5. Current limiting strategies for asymmetrical faults

Current limiting strategies (Section 3) have been extensively studied for symmetrical faults. In these conditions, controlling the positive-sequence is effective to ensure self-preservation and support the grid

[121]. However, suppressing or not controlling the negative-sequence during asymmetrical faults could endanger the reliability of the grid due to: [122]:

1. Overvoltages in non-faulty phases: Managing only positive-sequence current could increase the voltage of non-faulty phases beyond their rated value. Overvoltages could damage or trip nearby devices.
2. Underusage of the inverter current capability: Positive-sequence current might be limited under some asymmetrical faults. In this conditions, the inverter will work below its rated current if negative-sequence is not controlled. [60]. As the fault current contribution of inverters is limited compared to SGs, maximizing current is critical.
3. Complex fault detection: Some protection devices rely on negative-sequence currents to detect faults. Hence, GFM inverters should manage this sequence, specially when SG penetration is low.

According to the latest reports from ENTSO-e, GFM inverters are expected to act as a sink for unbalances, emulating SGs behaviour [123]. They should provide a low negative-sequence impedance, sinking unbalanced currents to counteract the asymmetries in the grid voltage. The expected equivalent circuits for positive (superscript +) and negative-sequence (superscript -) are given in Fig. 19. Even if this behaviour is achievable in regular conditions, maximum current will usually be exceeded during asymmetrical faults. GFM inverters should effectively limit positive and negative-sequence individually, prioritizing them according to operator requirements.

This section will describe modified current limiting strategies (Section 3) that support asymmetrical faults. MS strategy is not covered, as the sequence control of GFL inverters is well known [124].

5.1. Current-based limiters

CS strategy implemented in *abc* frame have shown the merits of controlling each phase independently [79]. However, the independent limitation of phase currents will introduce an homopolar component in the setpoint, requiring a 4-wire system (three phase + neutral) to operate properly. In 3-wire systems, homopolar current does not have a path to flow, saturating the current controller. An strategy to remove the homopolar current setpoint in 3-wire systems is proposed in [49].

In 3-wire systems, only positive and negative-sequence currents can flow. Hence, a more common approach is to use magnitude or priority-based CS, attending to both sequences. The simplified diagram is given in Fig. 20, in which the CS limiter is shared among sequences. The magnitude limiter strategy considering both sequences is also known as elliptical limiter, and it has been implemented in both $\alpha\beta$ [107] and dq [47,98] frames. It will scale down the current setpoint amplitudes, without changing the phase nor relative amplitudes between the sequences. Hence, positive to negative-sequence current ratio remains unchanged. To achieve sequence prioritization capability, priority-based CS has also been suggested [95]. The proposed algorithm can prioritize (1) phase balancing (negative-sequence) or (2) voltage magnitude recovery (positive-sequence).

5.2. Voltage-based limiters

Authors have extended the TVI concept to both positive and negative-sequence, ensuring the voltage source behaviour for both sequences [98,125,126]. In [125], a virtual resistor approach ensures the maximum current utilization of the converter for different asymmetrical faults. In [98], a priority-based TVI has been proposed. Its conceptual diagram and equivalent circuit are given in Fig. 21. The dynamic impedance will maximize the current in one sequence, whereas the remaining sequence will depend on the headroom capacity that is left out.

Table 5
Performance of current limiting strategies attending to LVRT requirements.

	MS	CS	TVI	VS		Summary
				PA	A	
Transient overcurrent limitation	+++	+++++	+++	+	++	Current-based limiters outperform voltage-based ones. CS provides the best performance, whereas MS performance is deteriorated due to fault detection and mode switch delay. Voltage-based limiters performance is limited due to two reasons: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The uncontrolled transient current due to the voltage source behaviour. • Limited bandwidth, specially when cascaded voltage-current control structures are used.
Fault current control						
Maximum current capacity	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Current-based limiters achieve this target. TVIs will not maximize fault currents under shallow sags, whereas VS will require some margin to face uncertainties under open loop control.
Decoupled active/reactive current	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	A PLL providing v_{pcc} magnitude and phase is required. When no PLL is used, active and reactive current becomes coupled due to PSL power unbalance, requiring some additional control action (e.g. dynamic power limiter in A-VS).
Transient synchronization stability						
Voltage sag	↓↓ as $Z_g \uparrow$	Low	Medium	↓↓ as $Z_g \uparrow$	High	Not using a PLL will make the system less susceptible to grid conditions (voltage sag depth, impedance or grid operation mode, e.g. islanded). Voltage-based limiters provide better transient performance. Current-based strategies will not only have a reduced stability, but they require additional anti-windup and re-synchronization strategies (MS) to properly recover from faults.
Phase jump	↓↓ as $Z_g \uparrow$	Low	Medium	↓↓ as $Z_g \uparrow$	None	

Fig. 19. Equivalent circuit of the GFM inverter for positive- and negative-sequence.

Fig. 20. Magnitude and priority-based CS for positive and negative-sequence.

Mixed strategies have also been suggested. These strategies will use a voltage-based limiter, such as a TVI [106] or VS [127] for the positive-sequence; and a CS for the negative-sequence [128]. The voltage-based limiter will ensure the voltage source behaviour in the positive-sequence. The current controller can be used to meet the negative-sequence current requirements of the grid code, injecting a current that depends on negative-sequence PCC voltage. The mixed

approach can also provide a prioritization strategy for the positive-sequence [127] or the negative one [106]. The conceptual diagram and equivalent circuit using a TVI is given in Fig. 22.

6. Stability enhancing strategies

Current limiting strategies relying on the PSL during the fault will eventually desynchronize if no stable equilibrium point is guaranteed.

Fig. 21. Priority-based approach using TVI for positive and negative-sequence.

Fig. 22. Mixed strategy for asymmetrical faults. TVI in the positive-sequence, CS in the negative-sequence.

In this context, literature has proposed transient stability enhancing strategies that could enlarge the time required for the inverter to desynchronize, or even provide an equilibrium point during the LVRT event.

This section reviews the stability enhancing strategies which are compatible with current limiting strategies from Section 3. This work does not consider those strategies which operate without current limitation [129] nor those which improve PLL-based strategies [130,131]. The strategies have been classified into two groups: (1) power synchronization loop based and (2) current saturation based strategies.

6.1. Power synchronization loop-based strategies

These strategies modify the inputs, the outputs or the parameters of the PSL. Hence, they can be used regardless of the current-limiting approach.

6.1.1. Power reference modification

In the power reference modification (PRM), the power setpoints (inputs of PSL) are modified during the fault. Reducing the active power setpoint can prevent the windup of the PSL, achieving a stable operation point and ensuring voltage source behaviour.

The most common approach consist on modifying power setpoints proportionally to PCC voltage, removing the need to detect the fault and switching between modes as shown in Fig. 23(a) [100]. Setpoints can also be modified to meet grid code fault current requirements [80] or to maximize the fault current [51]. It should be noted that depending on the tuning parameters, the dynamics the PSL and RPC (< 5 Hz [132]) could be slow compared to LVRT events. Additionally, power setpoints might not be tracked properly due to the droop behaviour.

PRM has been used with CS [80], TVI [133] and VS [73] strategies. As the TVI will impact the bandwidth of the outer loops, dynamic virtual resistors have been proposed as an alternative [100]. PRM has

also been used without any current limiting strategy [134]. However, the low outer loop dynamics cannot prevent transient overcurrents. Strategies to fasten the outer loops include reducing the damping power [135] or bypassing them [76].

6.1.2. Adaptive power synchronization

The inertia and damping of SGs is imposed by their electromechanical characteristics. However, these parameters are virtual in GFM inverters, and they can be dynamically tuned to damp oscillations faster [136] or to ensure stability under different grid conditions [137].

The adaptive power synchronization (APS) strategy aims to reduce δ drifts during faults. This is achieved by modifying the parameters of the PSL. In the case of a swing equation-based PSL (8), the typical approach is to increase the inertia and/or the damping power [138]. This strategy will not ensure a SEP during the fault, but it will reduce the rate of change of δ , increasing the time that a voltage sag can be handled before losing synchronism. A simplified diagram is shown in Fig. 23(b).

The APS has been used with both CS [92] and TVI [97,139] limiters. PSL parameters could change according to current or voltage conditions. However, the former can lead to negative side effects when the overcurrent occurs due to other phenomena, such as phase jumps [139]. In this scenario, the dynamics of the system are reduced and transient overcurrent will increase. Hence, using voltage conditions is advantageous.

APS strategy will provide good results if the grid frequency is kept constant and there are no phase jumps. An excessive modification of outer loop parameters could also lead to instability issues [140]. To prevent an excessive drift in parameters, APS and PRM could be used together [93].

6.1.3. Freeze angular speed

This approach consist on freezing the angular speed at the output of the PSL. Freezing the angular speed can improve the transient

Fig. 23. Simplified diagram of PSL-based transient enhancing strategies.

stability of both GFL and GFM inverters [141], and it was included as a requirement in the GB draft grid code for GFM inverters during fault conditions [142]. This approach is equivalent to setting an infinite inertia in the swing equation, or making the droop null in droop-based controllers [86]. A simplified diagram is shown in Fig. 23(c).

This strategy has been applied together with CS and TVI current limiters [54]. As in APS, voltage-based triggering can prevent poor performance against other voltage transients [142]. Authors in [86] have suggested freezing the angular speed to a value slightly lower to ensure that CS is exit once the fault is cleared. In grids composed of SGs and GFM inverters, freezing the angular speed at the weighted mean value of SG rotor speeds can improve the transient performance, at the cost of additional communication [143].

As the APS, this strategy will provide the best results if the grid frequency is kept constant, without phase jumps. It also requires a fault detection algorithm to disable and re-enable the PSL during the fault.

6.2. Current saturation-based strategies

CS strategies have proved to be effective against transient overcurrents. However, the transient stability is drastically reduced compared with voltage-based limiters. Several stability enhancing strategies that are specific for CS can be found in literature.

6.2.1. Voltage-based frequency feedforward

Adding a voltage-based feedforward to the PSL is an effective strategy to improve transient stability under events that do not trigger overcurrents [144]. Moreover, it is also an effective for GFM inverters using CS-based current limiting strategies [88]. A simplified diagram of the voltage-based frequency feedforward is shown in Fig. 24(a), in which the feedforwarded voltage is the q-component of v_o .

When the CS strategy of the GFM inverter is not active, the feedforward will resemble the damper winding of SGs: it will provide damping power during frequency excursions, whereas its impact in steady-state will be minimum. When the CS is activated, the voltage control capability will be lost and a steady q-component will appear in the voltage. In this scenario, the angular frequency of power converter will be modified by the feedforward path, ensuring a stable operation point if a proper gain is selected.

Instead of a proportional gain in the feedforward, a PI regulator can also be used to combine the swing equation with the basic principle of a PLL [118]. In any case, this strategy is fault detection and mode switching free.

6.2.2. Reactive power synchronization

A reactive power-based synchronization during fault has been proposed in [94]. A simplified diagram is shown in Fig. 24(b). According to the authors, calculating ω using reactive power can provide a stable equilibrium point for the converter, regardless of the voltage sag depth and duration. Moreover, compared to the active power-based synchronization, the equilibrium point during the fault is closer to the post-fault operation point, reducing the fault recovery time.

This strategy requires a fault detection and mode switching technique. It also requires information about the grid impedance. The accuracy of the method will depend on the performance of the impedance estimation algorithms.

6.2.3. Virtual power

The virtual power strategy uses the unsaturated current references to calculate the power feedback for the outer loops, while saturated currents are used for the inner controllers [145]. A simplified diagram is shown in Fig. 24(c).

This strategy will reduce the grid impedance seen by the PSL, modifying the VPA curve (7). At high saturation levels, the exchanged active power will only be limited by the filter and virtual impedance. Depending on the voltage sag depth and current capabilities of the inverter, a stable operation point can be achieved. Moreover, it has proved to be effective against other voltage perturbations, such as phase jumps or frequency excursions [52].

This approach still requires a proper anti-windup of the voltage controller, or a virtual admittance approach to prevent inner controller windup.

6.2.4. Internal voltage anti-windup

It aims to improve the transient synchronization by modifying the internal voltage amplitude and angular speed according to the current saturation level. Its simplified diagram is shown in Fig. 24(d). Even if transient stability can be improved by using the anti-windup on the PSL loop, extending the strategy to the RPC will prevent the windup of the voltage controller. However, this approach requires an RPC with an integral action, which is not always available.

This strategy has proved to be effective not only against voltage sags [128], but also against overloading conditions [85] and fluctuations of the DC power source in RES based systems [146].

6.3. Summary

Table 6 summarizes the main characteristics of the transient enhancing strategies. It includes information about the compatibility with previously discussed current limiting strategies, the performance against different voltage perturbations, the fault detection requirement and the voltage source behaviour capability.

Fig. 24. Simplified diagram of CS-based transient enhancing strategies.

Table 6
Main characteristics of transient improving strategies.

	Current limiting strategy			Voltage perturbation		Voltage source behaviour	SEP	Fault detection	References
	CS	TVI	VS	Sag	Overload				
Power reference modification	x	x	x	x	x	Yes	Yes	No	[48,76,80,100,133–135,147]
Adaptive power synchronization	x	x	x	x		Depends on limiter	No	No	[92,93,96,97,99,138,139]
Freeze angular speed	x	x	x	x		Depends on limiter	No	Yes	[54,86,142,143]
Voltage-based frequency feedforward	x			x		No	Yes	No	[88,118,125,144]
Reactive power synchronization	x			x		No	Yes	Yes	[94]
Virtual power	x			x	x	No	Yes	No	[52,145]
Internal voltage anti-windup	x			x	x	No	Yes	No	[85,128,146]

7. Open issues and challenges

Transient overcurrent limitation, fault current contribution and transient synchronization stability have been identified as the three main targets that IBRs, and hence, GFM inverters, should meet during LVRT. Despite the research efforts, there are no dominant current limiting strategies in existing literature. Strategies that provide a proper transient overcurrent limitation usually have a limited transient synchronization stability and vice versa. Transient enhancing strategies have been proposed to face this issue, but the complexity of the controller is increased. Hybridization of strategies is also an interesting approach. Moreover, the control of the active and reactive currents during the fault is usually not straightforward, making it difficult to meet grid code requirements. Additionally, research on asymmetrical faults is also required for a proper deployment of GFM inverters. In this sense, prioritization strategies of positive and negative sequence support is a key topic. Further research in this topic are expected in the future years.

Apart from the previously discussed topics, there are still open issues that require research and are open to improvements:

7.1. Regulatory framework

GFM inverters are a new technology that does not have a clear definition in most grid codes. It is usually referred to those converters that “maintain the internal voltage phasor constant or nearly constant in the sub-transient to transient time frame” [148]. However, this definition is not valid during overloading conditions. A unique and clear definition must be implemented in all the grid codes to create the basis for establishing a common standard for developing these converters.

Efforts for developing specific GFM codes are being carried out, such as the draft code developed by National Grid [132]. This code puts emphasis in the immediate response in LVRT, reflecting the voltage source behaviour of the GFM inverters. The same is true for the analysis in the ENTSO-E report [26] In this line, the latest draft grid code requires that the phase, magnitude and frequency of the internal voltage to remain fixed during faults. The amplitude of the current can be limited to prevent overcurrents, but keeping the phase relative to the voltage source not modified. In the meantime, GFM and GFL inverters should meet the same fault requirements.

7.2. Transient stability under high penetration of GFM inverters

The transient stability of GFM inverters under faults can be studied both analytically and numerically [43]. Analytical methods, such as the VPA, can be used to tune the controller parameters and optimize the transient performance. However, due to their complexity, they are limited to a single IBR connected to an ideal grid or equivalent SG. Numerical methods are a better approach to extend the study to several interconnected IBRs, but they difficult parameter optimization. Fault transient stability under different scenarios needs to be assessed more into detail, e.g., including different penetration of GFM and GFL inverters or using mixed current limiting strategies.

7.3. Transient voltage stability

Most of the literature has focused on the transient stability from the angle perspective. However, transient voltage stability issues have also been identified, especially when reactive power is prioritized, such as in GFM static compensators. Unlike angle stability, voltage instability only happens in an unidirectional way, when the absorbed reactive power goes over a limit, collapsing the voltage. Even if some strategies have been proposed to face this issue, research efforts are still required on this topic [149].

7.4. Current limitation under other transients

Despite voltage sag being the most studied transient in GFM literature, there are other scenarios that require a current limitation to prevent hardware damage. Among them, frequency excursions due to sudden change in the active power balance, phase jumps due to the tripping of lines or DC power source limits in stochastic sources. Compared to fault induced voltage sags, these events differ in two main aspects: (1) voltage level is not modified largely, and (2) transient dynamics are much lower [150]. Different approaches have been suggested to force the overloaded source to transfer the load to other sources [145]. However, there is no standardized approach. Moreover, these approaches usually turn the PSL into non-linear and modify its dynamics, requiring further research on its stability.

7.5. GFM inverter based protection systems

The effect of GFM inverters in AC fault protection systems is still in an early state compared to GFL inverters. Even if GFM inverters can mimic SGs due to the voltage source behaviour, the current contribution is far below conventional machines. Studies must evaluate if regular protection schemes are appropriate and effective long-term solution for a grid with significant proportion of IBRs, or whether a new protection paradigm is needed. Under large-scale integration of GFM inverters, the fault characteristics will depend on converter control. New AC protection schemes might have to consider the cooperation of converter control and protection hardware.

The interaction of anti-islanding protections with IBRs is also aggravated when GFM control strategies are used. Traditional GFL inverters will shut off without the presence of an external grid signal. GFM inverters can sustain a stable islanding operation, but they could also energize islanded systems without awareness of the unintentional island situation [151]. A robust set of standards are necessary for autonomous and grid-connected mode, balancing performance and protection requirements.

8. Conclusions

This work has carried out a comprehensive review of LVRT strategies for GFM inverters, focusing on those strategies that limit the current and enhance the transient stability, both under symmetrical and asymmetrical events.

Current limiting strategies are required due to the voltage source behaviour of the GFM converter, which produces overcurrents during voltage perturbations. Existing strategies have been described and classified into two main groups attending to the behaviour during the fault: voltage-based or current-based. Their performance has been compared attending to LVRT requirements: self protection (transient current limitation) and fault current contribution and transient synchronization stability. Even if current-based limiters are more extended, no strategy stands out: current-based limiters are better in managing transient overcurrents, whereas voltage-based limiters provide higher stability. All in all, research efforts are still required on this topic.

The modification of current limiting strategies to handle asymmetrical faults has also been discussed. During these events, both positive and negative sequence currents need to be handled to meet current limitation and fault current contribution of the operator. In most cases, due to the limited current capability of the power converters, a prioritization strategy of the positive and negative sequence will be required. In this context, during an asymmetrical fault, GFM inverters could prioritize voltage amplitude and phase balancing, or voltage magnitude boosting.

Regardless of the current limiting strategy, the transient synchronization stability of the GFM will be endangered during the LVRT event. This review has also covered the strategies to enhance the stability. Transient enhancing strategies will not limit the current, but they will ensure that the power converter keeps synchronized during the LVRT. These strategies have been classified into two main groups. Those based on the PSL loop modification, and which can be used with any current limiting strategy; and those which are only compatible with current saturation based strategies. This classification reveals the predominant use of current saturation strategies in the literature, which are characterized by their limited transient stability, requiring more effort than other strategies from stability perspective.

Finally, open issues and challenges related to the LVRT of GFM inverters have been addressed. The need for a specific regulatory framework stands out, which will set the foundations of GFM inverters in the power grid. In the meantime, several research efforts are required to delve deeper into the impact of GFM inverters in LVRT, such as evaluating the grid performance under high penetration of these converters, the impact on the protection systems, the transient stability from voltage perspective and the evaluation of other voltage transients different from voltage sags.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Ander Ordoño: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Writing – original draft. **Alain Sanchez-Ruiz:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Markel Zubiaga:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Francisco Javier Asensio:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Jose Antonio Cortajarena:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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